

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PROSPECTS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article examines the principles of developing a tourism development strategy, which from the very beginning should be focused on three main areas: delineation of functions and definition of roles involved x parties in the process of coordinated work on the development of tourism infrastructure in the region or municipality as a whole; formulation of projects to be implemented, first of all measures that guarantee rapid return on investment; creation of professional marketing.

Keywords: marketing program, investment activity, prerequisites for industry development, tourism potential, economic development.

The modern tourism industry is one of the largest high-yield and most dynamic sectors of the world economy. Tourism accounts for about 10% of the world's gross national product, global investment, all jobs and global consumer spending. To attract investment in the development of tourism infrastructure, taking into account the specifics of this industry, it is necessary to put into effect organizational and economic mechanisms that stimulate investment any activity in other objects of the tourism industry.

Actively attracting investments in economic practices could make a significant contribution to the development of the infrastructure of the tourism industry in the territories of Azerbaijan liberated from occupation.

The condition for creating an effectively functioning system for managing investment processes in the tourism industry is to increase the scientific basis of management decisions in the field of investments, ensuring the interaction of such basic elements of the management system as principles, methods, management functions, tools that guide the implementation of investments new projects to achieve the required results and level of efficiency. These circumstances predetermine the need to form such a mechanism for managing the process of investing funds in the turbine business of economic entities of the national economy miki, which would ensure the achievement of the set goals of investment design, both in the strategic aspect and in the near future.

In addition, the efficiency of the investment management system in the tourism sector can be significantly increased due to government investment instruments of supporting tourism programs, preferential lending to business entities, ensuring a high level of investment attractiveness of objects of the national economy for foreign investors foreign and domestic investors, promoting the accumulation of funds from small

financial investors credit institutions, institutional investors.

The success of tourism development directly depends on the level of government support for this industry.

The experience of local tourism operators has shown that the correct strategy and effective marketing program allow the company to identify target markets, develop permanent reliable partners, to definitely increase sales volume and market share.

The process of investment management (management of investment activities) represents a conscious, targeted regulation of all types of money, property and intelligence lectual values invested in business objects and other types of activities to generate profit (income) or achieve a social effect. Activation of investment activity depends on the presence of three main factors: investment opportunities, investment intentions and organizational structures capable of development management connections between organizations, consolidation of interests and opportunities, facilitating the effective implementation of investment projects aimed at improving technology legal relations. Developed tourism, thanks to the large flow of visitors, provides the region, first of all, with monetary income coming from outside and additional trade turnover.

Developing tourism potential is a relatively simple task in the presence of two essential prerequisites: there is a special "magnet" for visitors, this can there is some special attraction, churches, museums, unique architectural structures of their kind, or exceptional nature and opportunities for sports;

- in the immediate vicinity there is a fairly high potential of clients, which can lead to the emergence of large flows of visitors.

However, in many regions that have the necessary potential, it has not yet been used effectively enough.

Often, even with a significant number of visitors due to the underdevelopment of the tourism infrastructure and the lack of a comprehensive tourism offer, tourism brings some tangible income to the region. Tourists are often forced to bring food and everything they need for vacation with them from home; as a result, they leave only garbage, but not money, in their places of residence.

The comprehensive development of the existing tourism potential is complicated by the fact that in order to comprehensively resolve the issue, all numerous participants must unite their efforts business and stakeholders in order to create and implement a common vision that ultimately benefits everyone.

Generalized recipes for the successful development of tourism in many regions that have the necessary tourism potential can be formulated as follows:

- pragmatic start with small steps that can be quickly implemented and do not require attracting large capital;
- involvement of all participants, especially small businesses, in the development of a joint concept and coordination of the process on the part of the local administration;
- focus of the tourism offer on residents of nearby large cities, primarily on tourists coming for one day or for a short vacation,
- cooperation in advertising and cooperation with travel companies. When embarking on systematic measures aimed at the comprehensive development of tourism, one should keep in mind: tourism contributes to the development of enterprises, the creation of new places of business, the growth of the logical potential of the territory, creates new economic impulses in regions and municipalities. In addition, tourism improves the image of the region as an economically developed territory in its entirety. The work carried out in this direction will quickly pay off. In many regions and cities, as well as subjects of the country, in the case of concentration of forces on the development of tourism, success is ensured for local government bodies, and this means successful development local economy.

Tourism represents only one segment of economic development, but given certain prerequisites and conditions, it can become the main and most profitable direction of economic development of a country or region.

The development (formulation) of a tourism development strategy from the very beginning should be focused on three main areas:

- delimitation of functions and determination of the roles of the parties involved in the process of coordinated work on the development of tourist infrastructure in the region or municipality as a whole;
- formulation of projects to be implemented, first of all activities that guarantee rapid return on investment;
- creation of professional marketing.

In many regions there are a number of attractive centers for tourists, which are already acting as magnets

for visitors. However, at the same time, there is a significant deficit in other areas, as a result of which the use of tourism potential is still very weak and does not bring tangible economic benefits result.

Regions of the country, thanks to their attractions and historical monuments, can be competitive in the medium and long term and in international tourism. Creation of appropriate prerequisites, expansion of infrastructure and formation of a comprehensive package of tourism services are necessary prerequisites for the formation of tourism to one of the budget-forming sectors of the domestic economy.

Recently, tourism has received significant development and has become a massive socio-economic phenomenon on an international scale. Its rapid development is supported by the expansion of political, economic, scientific and cultural ties between states and peoples of the world. Mac's development of tourism allows millions of people to expand their knowledge of the history of their Fatherland and other countries, to get acquainted with the sights, culture, traditions of one or another trans.

The experience of the leading countries of the modern world clearly proves the need for highly developed and efficient small businesses in any national economy or sector. Therefore, the revival of the country cannot be achieved without the corresponding development of this sector of the economy, since it is he who is the locomotive that literally protects economic and social development. But at the same time, not enough attention is paid to studying the influence of small businesses on structural transformations of the regional economy, the formation of a rational structure industrial centers based on the development of small business, development of economic interaction between territorial authorities and small business, complex methodology Conducting assessments of entrepreneurial projects and conducting their examination in individual projects cities and regions, conditions unusual for industrialized countries.

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